

**Analysis of 26 Studies of the Impact of Coconut Oil on Lipid Parameters:
Beyond Total and LDL Cholesterol** by Mary T. Newport, M.D. and Fabian M. Dayrit, Ph.D.

Appendix B: Supplementary Table S1

Table S1. Differences in lipid profiles with standard deviations as reported in 26 studies of people consuming coconut oil by duration of study, including 29 groups totaling 984 lipid profile data sets for 792 distinct individuals. Values for TChol, LDL-C, and TG that did not change or decreased are highlighted in green; values for total cholesterol, LDL-C, and TG that increased are highlighted in yellow; values for HDL-C that increased are shown in blue; values for HDL-C that decreased are shown in gray. Base = baseline value Diff = difference; mos = months; NR=not reported; SD = standard deviations; wks = weeks

Study/Year	Summary: Lipid Profile Results for 29 Groups in 26 Studies of People Consuming Coconut Oil, by Duration of Study																	
	Duration	# Subjects	Total Cholesterol (mg/dL)				LDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)				HDL-Cholesterol (mg/dL)				Triglycerides (mg/dL)			
			Base	Diff	%	SD (±)	Base	Diff	%	SD (±)	Base	Diff	%	SD (±)	Base	Diff	%	SD (±)
Long Duration 1 to 2 years																		
Vijayakumar 2016 [1]	1 year	96	149.8	-5.23	-3.5	30.9	90.3	0.73	0.81	20.7	40.8	1.61	3.95	9.5	115.0	-2.96	-2.6	50.2
Vijayakumar 2016 [1]	2 years	96	149.8	-0.61	-0.4	28.6	90.3	0.75	0.83	21.8	40.8	2.42	5.93	10.8	115.0	-5.64	-4.9	47.1
Medium Duration 8 to 24 weeks																		
Mendis 1990 [2]	8 wks	25	179.4	-1.2	-0.6	15.1	114.1	-4.3	-3.7	14.3	42.5	1.5	3.6	10.4	125.8	2.7	2.1	36.3
Oliveira-de-Lira 2018 [3]	8 wks	18	215.6	-17.6	-8.1	17.6	143.2	-14.9	-10.4	17.7	52.9	2.7	5.0	6.4	130.9	-32.6	-24.9	29.1
Korrapati 2019 [4]	8 wks	9	193.0	0.0	0.0	16.1	125.0	-3.0	-2.4	13.9	46.1	4.8	10.4	3.4	106.0	-7.0	-6.6	24.0
Chinwong 2017 [5]	8 wks	32	190.4	-2.7	-1.4	18.0	116.6	-6.1	-5.2	17.7	60.3	3.9	6.5	NR	67.8	-3.1	-4.6	NR
Jeyakumar 2023 [6]	8 wks	22	172.0	14.0	8.1	5.9	113.0	13.0	11.5	2.2	35.0	-0.1	-0.3	17.9	117.0	7.0	6.0	12.3
Swarnamali 2024 [7]	8 wks	37	201.7	8.1	4.0	36.8	137.2	-2.0	-1.5	24.9	42.6	0.5	1.2	11.5	132.5	1.2	0.9	56.8
Assuncao 2009 [8]	12 wks	20	192.5	5.6	2.9	39.0	112.6	3.9	3.5	36.8	45.5	3.2	7.0	2.4	172.8	6.9	4.0	93.7
Teng 2024 [9]	12 wks	48	206.9	-19.3	-9.3	NR	130.3	-14.3	-11.0	NR	55.3	-5.0	-9.1	NR	105.4	-0.9	-0.8	NR
Cardoso 2015 [10]	3 mos	92	177.4	5.9	3.3	35.4	108.3	4.0	3.7	31.2	37.5	3.1	8.3	7.4	153.8	-2.0	-1.3	70.5
Vijayakumar 2016 [1]	3 mos	96	149.8	1.38	0.9	30.2	90.3	-0.98	-1.1	24.6	40.8	0.02	0.0	10.9	115.0	-3.7	-3.2	24.8
Fernando 2023 [11]	24 wks	43	206.3	-6.7	-3.3	44.7	141.2	-10.4	-7.4	41.5	44.7	2.2	4.9	5.9	104.9	4.3	4.1	42.8
Short Duration 3 to 7 weeks																		
Heber 1992 [12]	3 wks	9	165.0	30.0	18.2	7.0	104.0	25.0	24.0	8.0	40.0	2.0	5.0	4.0	93.0	17.0	18.3	23.0
Lu 1997 [13]	3 wks	15	162.4	-9.3	-5.7	14.7	90.1	-2.3	-2.6	15.9	53.0	-3.5	-6.6	8.1	93.0	-13.3	-14.3	26.6
Schwab 1995 [14]	4 wks	15	186.8	0.8	0.4	6.2	112.1	-1.9	-1.7	4.6	59.9	-2.3	-3.9	2.7	80.6	-3.5	-4.4	8.0
Cox 1998 [15]	4 wks	37	212.7	-1.2	-0.6	35.2	137.7	8.9	6.5	29	42.5	4.3	10	10.4	156.8	-14.2	-9.0	82.4
Harris 2017 [16]	4 wks	12	219.6	18.2	8.3	24.1	124.0	13.5	10.9	27.2	63.9	6.6	10.3	18.8	117.2	-9.7	-8.3	80.6
Khaw 2018 [17]	4 wks	28	228.2	8.5	3.7	21.3	135.3	-3.5	-2.6	19.0	77.3	10.8	14.0	11.2	78.8	6.2	7.9	51.4
Maki 2018 [18]	4 wks	12	188.0	13.3	7.1	NR	123.0	5.7	4.6	NR	46.0	3.0	6.5	NR	92.5	5.5	5.9	NR
Nikooei 2021 [19]	4 wks	22	206.3	32.6	15.8	53.6	107.6	21.0	19.5	26.3	44.2	8.3	18.8	2.3	216.5	-44.4	-20.5	114.6
Setyawati 2023 [20]	30 days	68	247.7	-21.1	-8.5	8.1	179.6	-38.2	-21.2	7.2	39.9	9.4	23.5	2.3	192.8	-9.2	-4.8	5.0
Reiser 1985 [21]	5 wks	16	158.0	10.0	6.3	3.0	96.0	14.0	14.6	4.1	45.0	1.0	2.2	1.1	80.0	-2.0	-2.5	3.6
Voon 2011 [22]	5 wks	45	182.1	9.3	5.1	26.7	118.3	9.3	7.8	29.0	47.6	5.4	11.4	11.6	85.0	-5.3	-6.2	34.5
Cox 1995, Men [23]	6 wks	13	251.4	3.7	1.5	34.0	166.3	4.7	2.8	33.0	46.4	-1.4	-3.0	6.0	203.7	27.3	13.4	97.0
Cox 1995, Women [23]	6 wks	15	239.8	3.3	1.4	24.0	154.1	1.9	1.3	25.0	69.6	-1.6	-2.3	11.0	124.0	-9.0	-7.3	27.0
McKenney 1995 #1 [24]	6 wks	11	222.3	11.0	4.9	19.0	149.0	6.4	4.3	19.5	49.8	4.1	8.2	15.9	117.1	2.9	2.5	47.7
McKenney 1995 #2 [24]	6 wks	17	214.0	-5.7	-2.7	20.0	138.6	-12.8	-9.2	12.8	50.9	5.2	10.2	12.4	122.3	9.5	7.8	64.8
Vogel 2020 [25]	45 days	15	180.1	-8.6	-4.8	49.4	112.5	-11.5	-10.2	37.2	39.4	3.7	9.3	14.9	141.0	-2.2	-1.6	78.3

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